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REVIEW ARTICLE

Diagnosis and Treatment of Children Cerebral Palsy with Method Resonance Medicine

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ABSTRACT

The article discusses two forms of resonance in medicine in the treatment of Children Cerebral Palsy. The first form is the destruction resonance. It is well known and we have used it to destroy, for example, tumors. The second form of resonance is the resonance of creation. It leads to the restoration of degenerated or destroyed organs. We have used the resonance of creation to repair organs affected by disease and to restore the immune system in patients.

Introduction

In our previous works [1-3] and in monographs [4-9] considered two options for using resonance in medicine - the resonance of destruction and the resonance of creation. Resonance has been used for many years in the treatment of various diseases [1-9]. In this paper, we will consider the possibilities of effective treatment of Children Cerebral Palsy using the methods resonance of creation. In the diagnosis and treatment of bioresonance therapy, the so-called "nosodes" are used - wave copies of various diseases, including oncological ones, and "organopreparations" - wave copies of normally functioning organs. A feature of the use of nosodes and organopreparations in our work was that we used not only low potencies of nosodes and organopreparations, but also high ones [4-9], while in previous works we used only low potencies of nosodes and organopreparations [4-9].

The diagnosis and treatment of Children Cerebral Palsy are preceded by a brief introduction to what is called "resonance."

From a technical point of view, resonance is a phenomenon of the response of an oscillatory system to external influences. When the periods of influence and response of the system coincide, resonance occurs - a sharp increase in the amplitude of the oscillations under consideration.

Resonance was discovered by Galelei G [10]. The resonance can be most clearly described as follows. A platoon of soldiers approaches the wooden bridge and the officer gives the command to go out of step because if a platoon of soldiers crosses the wooden bridge in step, the bridge can collapse from resonance. The vibrations of the bridge will coincide with the vibrations of the marching soldiers, a resonance will arise, from which the bridge will collapse.

In this review, the role of the bridge is "played" by the disease, and the role of the marching soldiers is "performed" by the therapeutic effect. The soldier

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commander did not want the bridge to collapse due to the possible resonance. The physician, by contrast, absolutely needs resonance to destroy the disease.

Resonant methods for the study of matter have found wide application in physics, chemistry, biology, and medicine. For example, Nuclear Magnetic Resonance (NMR).

At the end of the 20th century, the method of Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI) was developed on the basis of NMR. It is used to obtain images of the human brain, heart, and organs of the digestive tract. For the development of MRI in 2003, the American biophysicist Paul Lauterbur and his English colleague Peter Mansfield were awarded the Nobel Prize in Physiology or Medicine.

This is due to the fact that high potency drugs lead to an exacerbation of diseases. This circumstance extremely limits the possibility of their use, although there is an understanding that the higher the potency of the drug, the more effective it is.

So, the term "drug potency" is actively used not only in homeopathy, but also in such a direction of medicine, which is called bioresonance therapy.

Let us briefly touch on what the "potency of drugs" is and how they are obtained. It has been established that the greater the potency of the drug, the higher its effectiveness.

In 1975, the German doctor Frank Morell came to a completely logical conclusion that if a disease of the organs of the human body is inevitably accompanied by disturbances in their frequency rhythm, then the essence of treatment should be to suppress the emerging "unhealthy" vibrations and restore normal ones.

Vegetative resonance test - VRT, originally proposed in 1991 by the German scientist Schimmel G [11], allows one-point examination. Testing only one biologically active point with it makes it possible to assess the state of not only all organs and systems, but also their interconnection.

A computer-based device for bioresonance therapy was created, which included both diagnostic and therapeutic parts. In a modern device for bioresonance therapy there is a large selector with diagnostic (they are also therapeutic) markers, information copies of diseases, which are called "nosodes" when it comes to a disease and "organopreparations" - information copies of healthy organs when a doctor deals with normal, not pathological organs or their parts. "Nosodes" are necessary for the identification and treatment of diseases and "organ products" for testing perfectly healthy organs or their parts. Nosodes are electronic markers about a disease and "organ products", information markers about a healthy organ or its part, recorded on a certain medium.

Each test drug has a wave effect on the patient. It is necessary to restore the spectral (frequency) harmony of the patient.

Resonance of Destruction

Diagnostics using fracture resonance

Destruction resonance has been used for over two hundred years, exactly as long as homeopathy has existed. The homeopathic doctor creates such a relationship between the drug and the pathological process in the patient, in which the periods of exposure and response of the system coincide and a resonance occurs - a sharp increase in the amplitude of oscillations, as a result of which the pathological focus is destroyed.

In the activity of a doctor using bioresonance therapy, a similar process takes place using modern technologies. Diagnostics is performed first. For this, the nosode of the alleged disease is displayed on the computer screen connected to the device for bioresonance therapy, and it is tested in the patient. If the nosode is "not tested", then there is no resonance and the arrow on the computer screen does not fall down in the middle of the screen. Therefore, the patient does not have the disease that is displayed by the nosode. In the same case, if the nosode is tested, a resonance arises between the patient and the test drug - the arrow on the computer screen falls and indicates that the patient has the disease, the name of which is the nosode. This is a diagnostic resonance, but not a curative one. This is how resonance diagnostics are carried out in bioresonance therapy.

Healing using destruction resonance

To treat the identified disease, the doctor must destroy either the tumor or the infectious process with the help of resonance, and for this it is necessary to potentiate the nosode identified in the patient, i.e. find the potency of the nosode that will resonate with the pathological process in the patient and destroy the disease, in other words, a therapeutic resonance is needed. To do this, find that potency of the nosode (usually high), which leads to the fact that when testing this nosode in a patient, the arrow stops falling. Such a potency of the nosode leads to a resonant destruction of the structures of the disease. In other words, the informational content of the nosode in a certain potency is used for the resonant destruction of the structure of the disease, namely the treatment of the found disease. The doctor writes down the information content of the potentiated nosode on the sugar crumbs and the patient takes this sugar crumbs and is thus treated, i.e. there is a resonant destruction of the structure of the disease.

The use of bioresonance therapy for the treatment of various diseases only of extremely low potencies, as in classical homeopathy, did not allow and does not allow

to effectively treat many diseases, including oncological diseases, many infectious diseases, etc. In other words, for many years there has been a crisis in bioresonance therapy, and thus, in general, in resonance medicine. This can be seen in the materials of the annual scientific conferences on bioresonance therapy [11].

When it is said that drugs are used in works that exceed the LM potency of drugs, they mean those potencies that are prepared electronically [1-9].

The prepared classical homeopathic preparations and the electronic potentiation preparations, which are used in bioresonance therapy, do not fundamentally differ from each other. We have not seen in the literature indications of the difference between homeopathic preparations prepared by the usual, classical method and preparations of electronic potentiation.

Since 2016, materials have been published on the use of high potency drugs for treatment [8-13]. It was found that drugs of high and ultra-high potency do not cause any side effects, including toxic effects on sick and healthy people. However, high potency drugs have proven to be extremely effective in the treatment of severe and extremely serious diseases such as cancer, infectious diseases, including HIV, stones and cysts in organs [4-9]. In particular, metastatic forms of oncology are effectively treated. It has been established that all those forms of oncological diseases that are in the selector of the device for bioresonance therapy are effectively treated with drugs of high and ultra-high potencies.

Treatment of patients with nosode preparations exceeding the high potency was not an end in itself. This method has been found in medical practice.

So, resonance medicine, in addition to homeopathy, includes resonance diagnostics and resonance therapy. Treatment of patients in whom the structure of the disease, for example, oncology, is destroyed, is called "destruction resonance".

Resonance of creation

Since 2016, materials have been published on the use of the second direction of therapeutic resonance - "resonance of creation" [1-9]. Resonance can not only destroy, for example, diseases, but also create lost biological structures. This made it possible to treat degenerative diseases.

We could not find in the scientific literature an idea of that resonance can be not only a "resonance of destruction", but also a "resonance of creation". This is obviously due to the fact that it is not easy to imagine how the coincidence of frequencies leads to a response that is not destructive, but constructive. In this review, we have presented illustrations of how resonance can be not only destructive, but also

constructive, in particular for the treatment of degenerative diseases.

In the treatment with the help of the resonance of destruction, nosodes of diseases were used, from which preparations in the F potency were prepared. This principle has not been effective in the treatment of degenerative diseases. The creation and formation of the principle of "resonance of creation" became possible only as a result of the fact that not nosodes, but organopreparations exceeding the LM potency were used for treatment. Without organopreparations in the F potency, it is impossible to imagine the use of this principle.

This review presents material related to the treatment of degenerative diseases. This means that treatment is nothing more than the process of restoring organs or organ systems that have undergone changes as a result of diseases or as a result of an aging degenerative process.

Degenerative diseases can also be congenital. It is clear that a significant part of congenital diseases is a consequence of the underdevelopment of an organ or organ system.

In practice, most often after an illness, for example, inflammation, or as a result of the senile process, the level of health of the organ falls down to its destruction. Such an organ requires restoration (rehabilitation). The resonance of creation makes it possible to restore an organ or part of it.

Organopreparations are wave preparations (wave copies) of healthy organs or parts of them. Nosodes are wave drugs of the disease.

In the selectors of hardware and software complexes for bioresonance therapy, there are various organopreparations. For the restoration, rehabilitation of organs, we used organopreparations in the F potency. They were done in the same way as the F potency nosodes.

Treatment of the Degenerative Process Using the Resonance Method Creation

We find the potency of the organopreparation that leads to resonance with the affected organ, namely, the termination of testing this organ or organ section as problematic. In this case, the arrow stops falling on the computer screen. It is a therapeutic resonance, but not diagnostic. The doctor prepares preparations of healthy organs for the patient in the F potency, writes them down on the sugar crumbs, which the patient takes.

Children Cerebral Palsy

Children Cerebral palsy (CCP) is a group of movement disorders that appear in early childhood [12]. Signs and symptoms vary among people and over time [12,13], but include poor coordination, stiff muscles, weak muscles, and

tremors [12]. There may be problems with sensation, vision, hearing, and speaking [12]. Often, babies with cerebral palsy do not roll over, sit, crawl or walk as early as other children of their age [12]. Other symptoms include seizures and problems with thinking or reasoning, which each occur in about one-third of people with CP [12]. While symptoms may get more noticeable over the first few years of life, underlying problems do not worsen over time [12].

Cerebral palsy is caused by abnormal development or damage to the parts of the brain that control movement, balance, and posture [12,14]. Most often, the problems occur during pregnancy, but they may also occur during childbirth or shortly after birth [12]. Often, the cause is unknown [12]. Risk factors include preterm birth, being a twin, certain infections during pregnancy, such as toxoplasmosis or rubella, exposure to methylmercury during pregnancy, a difficult delivery, and head trauma during the first few years of life, among others [12]. About 2% of cases are believed to be due to an inherited genetic cause [15]. A number of subtypes are classified, based on the specific problems present [12]. For example, those with stiff muscles have spastic cerebral palsy, those with poor coordination in locomotion have ataxic cerebral palsy, and those with writhing movements have dyskinetic cerebral palsy [16]. Diagnosis is based on the child's development over time [12]. Blood tests and medical imaging may be used to rule out other possible causes [12].

CP is partly preventable through immunization of the mother, and efforts to prevent head injuries in children such as through improved safety [12]. There is no known cure for CP, but supportive treatments, medication and surgery may help many individuals [12]. This may include physical therapy, occupational therapy and speech therapy [12]. Medications such as diazepam, baclofen and botulinum toxin may help relax stiff muscles [12,17,18]. Surgery may include lengthening muscles and cutting overly active nerves [1]. Often, external braces and other assistive technology are helpful [12]. Some affected children can achieve near normal adult lives with appropriate treatment [12]. While alternative medicines are frequently used, there is no evidence to support their use [12].

Cerebral palsy is the most common movement disorder in children [19]. It occurs in about 2.1 per 1,000 live births. Cerebral palsy has been documented throughout history, with the first known descriptions occurring in the work of Hippocrates in the 5th century BCE [10]. Extensive study of the condition began in the 19th century by William John Little, after whom spastic diplegia was called "Little's disease" [20]. William Osler first named it "cerebral palsy" from the German zerebrale Kinderlähmung (cerebral child-paralysis) [21]. A number of potential treatments are being examined, including stem cell therapy [12]. However, more

research is required to determine if it is effective and safe [12].

Etiology of cerebral palsy

Cerebral palsy is a series of clinical syndromes, mainly from the motor sphere, which occur as a result of brain damage before childbirth (antenatal), during childbirth (intranatal) or in the first month of life (postnatally). Of every 100 cases of cerebral palsy, 30 occur prenatally, 60 intranatally, and 10 postnatally.

In the antenatal period, the main cause of the disease are

- Toxicosis of pregnancy,
- Immunological incompatibility
- Maternal and fetal blood, psychotrauma,
- Mechanical trauma to the abdomen,
- Acute and chronic infections,
- As well as decompensated diseases of the cardiovascular, endocrine system in the mother.

Intrapartum causes include

- Asphyxia,
- Birth traumatic brain injury.

In the postnatal period, the cause of cerebral palsy can be traumatic and infectious diseases of the nervous system, various intoxications, and radiation sickness.

The pathogenesis of cerebral palsy

Hypoxia, acidosis, hypoglycemia and other metabolic changes play the main role in the pathogenesis of the pathology of the nervous system, which develops in ante-, intra- and, partially, postnatally. Metabolic products can affect the brain directly or lead to edema and secondary circulatory changes.

Complex motor disorders in children with cerebral palsy occur as a result of the release of brainstem structures from subordinate influences of the cerebral hemispheres and cerebellum, which are delayed in their development and affected by one or another pathological process (inflammation, hypoxia, trauma, etc.). The consequence of the increase in the pathological activity of the structures of the trunk is the activity of unreduced tonic reflexes (cervical, labyrinthine, grasping, etc.) and violations of muscle tone, characteristic of all forms of the disease and determining their nosological unity. On the basis of this, pathological synergies and attitudes are formed in the joints of the shoulder and pelvic girdle, and later contractures.

Depending on the location in the brain of certain pathological processes, paresis, hyperkinesia, ataxia,

hypermetria, and other forms of motor deficiency may develop.

Pathological anatomy of cerebral palsy

The morphological picture of cerebral palsy at different stages of the disease manifests itself in different ways. Various intrauterine lesions of the brain lead to a violation of its formation, inflammatory changes in the brain tissue, anomalies in the development of the vascular network and, as a result, secondarily, to impaired cerebral circulation and hypoxia. These changes are aggravated under the influence of even mild intracranial birth trauma. Destructive-atrophic and inflammatory processes that began in the period of intrauterine development and continue in the early postnatal period develop mainly in the cortex and substance of the cerebral hemispheres, in the midbrain and in the cerebellar hemispheres. A feature of brain damage is its diffuseness.

There are two types of morphological changes in cerebral palsy. In some cases, we can talk about malformations of the brain, such as pachygyria, microgyria, underdevelopment of the occipital lobes or cerebellar lobes, etc., phenomena of hypo- and aplasia of individual lobules and even lobes of the brain, etc.

Resonant diagnosis of children cerebral palsy

In the selector of the device, we find the following organ preparations of degenerated formations of the brain in CCP, necessary for treatment: amygdala, basal nucleus, insular cortex, cerebral septum, hippocampus, neocortex, temporal lobe, parietal lobe, isocortex, pear-shaped lobe, insular field, pre-base of the hippocampus, paralimbic area of the cortex. All of these structures are tested in patients, i.e. the arrow falls when testing the listed organopreparations in patients. The nosode is also tested - Amyloid or Amyloidosis, brain plaques (neurotic plaques), prions. We test atherosclerosis as an extremely important cause of CCP.

It is important to pay attention to the fact that the identification of the above structures of the brain (they are tested) by testing is necessary for the diagnosis of CCP. There have been cases when the doctor does not detect any clinical symptoms of CCP, but tests the given configuration of the brain structures on the device.

Treatment of Children Cerebral Palsy by the Method of Resonance of Creation

After testing, resonance diagnostics, all of the listed organopreparations, treatment is carried out by the method of CCP creation resonance. The corresponding preparations are prepared from the tested organopreparations. They are recorded on sugar crumbs in the potency that is necessary for treatment and resonant treatment of patients is carried out.

Treatment of Patients with Early and Moderate Dementia

Treatment of all tested brain structures showed that the patient responds to this treatment quite adequately. In the course of treatment, the "insular cortex" was the first to be tested, followed by the "basal nucleus". As the testability of these brain structures decreased, the patient reported that his condition was getting significantly better, not only in terms of short-term memory recovery, but also in other indicators.

In patients with moderate dementia, in the first weeks of treatment, organopreparations, the islet cortex, the basal nucleus, the temporal lobe, the isocortex, and those characteristic of CCP - the lenticular nucleus, paranigral dopamine nuclei of the middle brain, "roof of the midbrain".

Subsequently, the hippocampus, piriform lobe, islet field, and hippocampal pre-basement were no longer tested. At the same time, the reports of the patients' relatives changed: "Our patient began to cry less, take offense at us less and began to recognize close people more often - children, grandchildren. It is also very important that it became easier for her to get up from the chair. Before starting treatment, getting up from a chair was a difficult and lengthy process for her. She became less touchy, and urinary incontinence became less common. "Treatment is carried out until complete loss of AD symptoms.

The foregoing testifies to the effective treatment of CCP by the method of resonance of creation [13].

Diagnosis and Treatment of Demyelination in Patients with Children Cerebral Palsy

It has been shown that the process of demyelination and, in general, multiple sclerosis can be effectively treated (cured) by the resonance of creation method [10-13].

It has been established that demyelination of nerve formations is essential in the pathogenesis of diseases of the nervous system. It has been established that in CCP there is a significant demyelination of nerve structures.

How does this circumstance affect the therapeutic process? Patients with CCP were tested for the presence of demyelination in them, especially those structures that are associated with the main symptoms of these diseases. It has been established that in these two diseases there is a distinct demyelination not only of those structures that are not directly related to the symptoms of these diseases, but also of those that are directly related to the manifestation of CCP.

Naturally, the question arose to what extent effective treatment of demyelination of these formations can improve the condition of patients with CCP stop or reduce the frequency

of relapses of the degeneration process? Preliminary testing of the state of nervous structures for the presence of a demyelination process in them indicated that these patients had a completely distinct process of demyelination, namely, local multiple sclerosis. That is why complex therapy was carried out, the treatment of these diseases not only of formations that have undergone degeneration, but also of local multiple sclerosis or demyelination. The potency of the myelin organ preparation (myelin sheath) was selected for patients, which corresponded to the level of their demyelination and was prescribed to patients with both CCP.

The results of the work showed that the inclusion of demyelination in the therapeutic process of treatment led to a significant improvement in the state of the nervous system in these patients - a significant decrease in the recurrence of degeneration and thereby prolonging the process of effective treatment. The results of this work indicate that additional treatment of the demyelinating process led to a qualitative improvement in the state of the nervous system compared to what took place without the inclusion of treatment for the demyelinating process. The process of restoring the nervous system not only accelerated sharply, but also increased the time of absence of recurrence of the disease.

The above indicates the effective treatment CCP by the method of resonance of creation [13].

Thus, the literature shows effective diagnosis and treatment of CCP. It follows from the above that the materials of this review article meet the three principles of evidence-based medicine - scientific character (resonance - scientific non-direction), efficiency and safety.

Thus, the literature shows effective diagnosis and treatment of CCP by the method of resonance of creation.

Thus, the materials of this review article meet the three principles of evidence-based medicine - scientific (resonance - scientific non-direction), efficiency and safety.

Diagnosis and Treatment of Cerebral Palsy with Bioresonance Therapy

Restoration of the structures of the nervous system

Parents came to the reception with their child Ya-vym M., 2.5 years old, suffering from cerebral palsy. At this age, the boy did not walk. The child was born prematurely with a weight of 1800 gr. By the age of 2.5 years, there was not only a delay in motor, but also in mental development. The boy had an extremely low vocabulary that he spoke. In addition, the child had dysplasia of the left hip joint.

During the examination, I found that the boy was being tested with the index (nosode) "Multiple sclerosis", and therefore the focus of attention for him was precisely multiple sclerosis. It seems to me that the patient had a

decrease in the amount of myelin in the structures of the nervous system. All the necessary range of nosodes was selected in high potency, including "multiple sclerosis", as well as the organ preparation "Myelin sheath".

Testing of the organ preparation showed that it is problematic not only in the spinal cord, but also in the brain.

Just as in the previous illustration of the treatment of a patient with cerebral palsy, we used a combined method, namely, destroying and creating resonance.

As a result of treatment for 3.5 months, the child's hip dysplasia disappeared, independent walking appeared without adult support for 5-6 steps, mental development improved significantly. We recorded the results of treatment with the help of video. As a result of treatment, the boy began to walk independently for 7, 10, and then 15 steps. Subsequently, the patient became completely free to walk.

It is important to note that I have used a high potency prion protein cassette. The preparations of this cassette were tested, which indicated that pathological prion proteins were present in the central nervous system of the child and it was necessary to eliminate these proteins.

Please note that cerebral palsy is also an autoimmune disease. That is why drugs for the treatment of the autoimmune process () are included in the treatment. We have successfully treated 19 patients with cerebral palsy.

In all cases of cerebral palsy, the nosodes of "multiple sclerosis", the organ preparation "myelin sheath" and in 8 patients the axial cylinder of nerves were tested. That is why the specific treatment of this disease with drugs in high potency gave a positive result.

Thus, for the treatment ((cure)) of patients with cerebral palsy, we used the principle of creative resonance, the principle of destructive resonance and the autoimmune process.

At the reception, patient T-va I., 11 years old, who for almost 10 years has developed an abnormal gait - she walked only on her toes all the time. The correct gait in children, starting from 1-1.5 years, is such that first the support is carried out on the heel, then on the entire foot, and only then on the toe.

The formation of walking in children of the first year of life is carried out in such a way that they begin to walk only on their toes, and only as they grow older do they have elements of walking, in which the child first stands on the heel, then on the entire foot, and only then rests on the toe. The final stage in the formation of normal walking in a child is the same walking as in adults - first, support is carried out on the heel, then there is a roll over the entire foot, and then support on the toe.

In contrast to how walking is carried out by peers, in our patient, it occurs only on toes. In other words, the patient did not progress in this element of walking, if the time is counted from the age of 7-12 months of life. This is due to a disease in the structures of the central nervous system.

Only with an effort of will can a girl force herself to first rely on the heel, then on the entire foot, and then on the toe.

Our patient at the first visit was also diagnosed with chronic tonsillitis, sinusitis, frontal sinusitis, adenoids.

From the anamnesis, it became clear that the pregnancy and childbirth of the girl's mother proceeded with serious complications. After a long period of labor activity in the mother (pregnancy with two fetuses with in vitro fertilization), she still had a caesarean section. A difficult pregnancy and childbirth, obviously, led to the changes that were revealed in the girl. Numerous attempts to treat walking disorders have not led to positive results.

During the examination, it was possible to identify problems in the lumbar spinal cord - in these structures, the nosodes of "Multiple sclerosis" and the organ preparation "Myelin sheath" were tested. From the first session, drugs in high potency of "Multiple Sclerosis" and "Myelin Sheath" were selected. In other words, the principle of the resonance of creation and the resonance of destruction was used in the treatment. In addition, a large number of streptococci and staphylococci were found in the girl, which led to the occurrence of sinusitis, frontal sinusitis, and adenoid vegetations. In this regard, cassettes in high potency of nosodes of microorganisms were used - treatment according to the principle of resonance of destruction.

After the start of treatment - on the second visit, I could not detect a walking disorder the same as on the first visit. The girl walked the way adults walk, i.e. first, the support is carried out on the heel, then on the entire foot, and then on the toe.

Testing on a hardware-software complex (vegetative resonance test) showed a decrease in problems in the spinal cord, namely, in its lumbar region. In other words, the nosode "multiple sclerosis" was tested significantly less.

- What has changed in your walking since the first visit to the medical center? - it was my question to the girl.
- I began to walk quite normally - first to rely on the heel, then on the entire foot, and only then on the toe.
- Maybe the changes are connected only with the fact that you force yourself to do it?
- No, it comes naturally to me.

Of course, all this instilled confidence that the doctor was on the right track in creating the technology that would effectively treat patients with cerebral palsy.

On the third visit to the medical center, the patient demonstrated her walking. She became even more confident compared to the previous days. I saw that the girl, when walking, now first supports the heel, then the entire foot, and finally the toe.

- Ira, tell me, please, now it has become easier for you to walk when the support on the foot is carried out as in adults or your peers. Maybe you don't care how you walk?

"Now it's easier for me to walk.

- Are you sure about that?
- Yes.
- Do you get tired less when walking like this or not?
- Certainly less. Now I don't get tired at all. When I walked on my toes, I got tired quickly, but now I don't.

During the examination, the changes for the better became quite obvious - the nosode "multiple sclerosis" was not tested, and the organ preparation "myelin sheath" was not tested as not normal. Ira's mother, with whom she came to the medical center, quite confidently said that her gait had become completely normal.

The above case indicates that the dominant factor in the pathogenesis of cerebral palsy, of course, is the process of demyelination of nerve structures. And the specific treatment of the manifestations of multiple sclerosis (using the principle of the resonance of creation and the resonance of destruction) in the patient led to the cure of the manifestations of cerebral palsy.

Conclusion

The problem of the treatment of CCP - remains very relevant. The review article for the first time presents an original and effective method of treating CXCP - the resonance of creation, which allow curing the disease. The method of resonance therapy is technically reliable, does not cause side effects and complications.

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